

Fluid-structure interaction during the water impact at high horizontal velocity of a thick plate: experimental data and simplified modelling

Iafrati, A.^{1*}

¹ CNR-INM¹ (INstitute of marine Engineering)
Rome, Italy (alessandro.iafrati@cnr.it)

ABSTRACT

The elastic deformations of a flat rectangular plate generated during the water entry at high horizontal velocity are investigated both experimentally and theoretically by using a simplified model to derive the out-of-plane displacement as well as the strain everywhere on the plate. Tests were performed on an aluminum plate thick enough to ensure that the deformation was always within the elastic regime. Measurements are provided in terms of pressures, strains and total hydrodynamic loads. The simplified model is a combination of a fluid-loading model, providing the pressure distribution at any time, and a structural model, similar to that proposed in Szilard (2004) and used also in Faltinsen (1999). The model is validated and tuned in one test condition before applying it to the analysis of other test cases. It is found that, although rather simple, it provides very accurate estimates of the strains, aside from some limits occurring at the sides due to the difficulty in correctly representing the boundary conditions.

Keywords: Fluid-structure interaction, Water entry, Potential flow, Modal analysis, Theory of elasticity

1. INTRODUCTION

In this paper the fluid-structure interaction taking place during the water entry of a flat plate with a high horizontal velocity component is investigated. The motivation for the study stems from the need of achieving a deeper understanding of the aircraft ditching, i.e. the emergency landing on water in controlled conditions. However, similar impact conditions are encountered by high speed planing crafts moving on rough sea or on the wetdeck of multihull vessels (e.g. Faltinsen et al., 1997). The phenomenon is highly transient, and generates large pressures and forces on the structure. Numerical simulations are rather challenging due to the high resolution needed to capture all the relevant phenomena (Seddon and Moatamedi, 2006).

In the naval field, the design is made by using a uniform (“equivalent”) pressure distribution over the hull surface, which is often based on guidelines classification society (Kim et al., 2008; Louarn and Manganelli, 2010; Stenius et al., 2011). However, when a plate impacts the free surface, important hydroelastic effects may enter into play, and thus further investigations based on strains measurements are necessary (Faltinsen et al., 1997). For the aircraft ditching, the design cannot aim at achieving the integrity of the structure after the ditching but mainly at enabling a safe evacuation of the occupants. The advancement in understanding the phenomenon was hindered by the difficulty in performing representative experiments and by the limits of the available computational tools.

Representative ditching experiments are discussed in Iafrati et al. (2015). In Iafrati (2015) data measured in high-speed ditching tests on aluminum and composite plates of different thickness are presented and discussed. It is shown that the more compliant is the plate, the higher are the maximum

¹ Formerly INSEAN, Marine Technology Research Institute

* Correspondence to: alessandro.iafrati@cnr.it

loads, denoting a significant role played by the fluid-structure interaction. Nevertheless, strains are measured by a limited number of strain gauges and do not allow to achieve a complete picture of what happens on the plate. In order to overcome such important limitation, a simplified model is developed here. The structural behavior is modelled by a modal expansion similar to that used in Faltinsen (1999) whereas the fluid loading is derived by assuming the pressure distributed as predicted by the self-similar solution of the two-dimensional water entry problem of the ditching plate (Iafrati, 2016). The self-similar profile is scaled in both length and intensity in order to match, at each time step, the wetted length and the total load measured in the tests. The simplified model is validated and tuned in the case of pitch angle 10 degrees, horizontal velocity 40 m/s, vertical velocity 1.5 m/s. Such test condition is among the ones leading to the highest loads and, furthermore, being one of those chosen to check the repeatability of the tests, results are considered as highly reliable (Iafrati et al., 2015).

2. EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

Experiments were performed at the CNR-INM high speed ditching facility. The facility is composed by an inclined guide, installed over the water basin. A trolley carrying the specimen to be tested, the acquisition system and the instrumentation runs along the guide. The guide can be rotated in order to achieve different V/U velocity ratios, V and U denoting the vertical and horizontal velocity components. The trolley is accelerated by a system of elastic cords and it is left to run freely along the guide shortly before the initial contact with water (CNR-INSEAN, 2012). Due to the quite large mass of trolley and acquisition box, more than 850 kg, the velocity reduction during the tests is quite small, less than five percent in the worst conditions.

Tests were performed on a plate made of aluminum alloy AL2024 T3, 1000 mm long and 500 mm wide. The thickness was 15 mm, which kept the deformation within the elastic regime in all conditions. Pitch angles of 4, 6 and 10 degrees, and horizontal velocity components 30, 40 and 45 m/s were considered. The plate was instrumented by 18 pressure probes and 6 biaxial strain gauges (Fig. 1) whereas the total hydrodynamic load acting normal on the plate was measured by 4 piezoelectric load cells. All signals were acquired onboard with a sampling rate of 200 kS/s for the pressures and 20 kS/s for strains and forces.

The plate was fixed by two rows of bolts to a L-shaped aluminum frame, 10 mm thick and 75 mm wide all around. The L-shaped aluminum frame was then fixed to the steel box containing the acquisition system. Further details on the facility and a detailed check of the test repeatability are provided in Iafrati et al. (2014, 2015).

3. SIMPLIFIED MODELING

3.1 Structural model

The experimental tests provide accurate measurements of the strains at different positions on the plate, but do not allow to completely reconstruct the strain field or the out-of-plane displacement. A rather reliable estimate of such information can be retrieved by a simplified structural model. Although, as discussed in the next section, the plate is forced by a time varying pressure distribution, the inertia of the plate is neglected and the structural model is based on quasi-static loading conditions.

Fig 1 Position of the strain gauges (Sx) and pressure probes (Pxx) on the plate

The structural response is described by using the classical theory for thin elastic plates, e.g. Szilard (2004). The model is derived under the assumption of a homogeneous, isotropic and linear elastic material, with the plate initially flat and thin, i.e. the constant thickness is small compared to other dimensions. More important, it is assumed that the deflection, $w(x,y,t)$, is always small (generally below one tenth) compared to the plate thickness and that the slope of the deflected surface is small compared to unity. Within such assumptions, the shear deformations and the normal stress in the direction transverse to the plate are neglected.

For a plate with uniform thickness, the governing differential equation of a plate with distributed loads is (Szilard, 2004)

$$\frac{\partial^4 w}{\partial x^4} + 2 \frac{\partial^4 w}{\partial x^2 \partial y^2} + \frac{\partial^4 w}{\partial y^4} = \frac{p(x, y, t)}{D} \quad (1)$$

where, as anticipated, inertia terms are neglected and $D = Eh^3/[12(1 - \nu^2)]$ is the flexural rigidity of the plate. The solution of equation (1) is here derived by using the Vlasov/Galerkin method (Szilard, 2004) which present the solution in the form:

$$w(x, y, t) = \sum_m \sum_n W_{mn}(t) X_m(x) Y_n(y) \quad (2)$$

where $X_m(x)$ and $Y_n(y)$ are two independent sets of functions that satisfy the boundary conditions.

As discussed in the previous section, the 15 mm uniform thickness plate is fixed by two rows of bolts to the L-shaped aluminum frame and then to the steel frame of the acquisition box. Although rather rigid, the boundary conditions cannot be considered as clamped all around and an elastic restraint conditions seems more appropriate. Several combinations of boundary conditions have been considered at the sides and based on the comparisons with experimental measurements the most appropriate combination is a clamped boundary condition in the longitudinal direction and an elastic restraint condition in the transverse direction, which is similar to what is done in Faltinsen (1999).

By assuming clamped boundary conditions at $x = 0$ and $x = a$, the eigenfunctions in the longitudinal direction are:

$$X_m(x) = \cosh u - \cos u - a_m(\sinh u - \sin u) \quad (3)$$

where $u = \lambda_m x/a$ and $a_m = (\cosh \lambda_m - \cos \lambda_m)/(\sinh \lambda_m - \sin \lambda_m)$. The eigenvalues satisfy the equation $\cos \lambda_m \cosh \lambda_m = 1$. In the transverse direction, it is assumed that the solution is symmetric with respect to the midline at $y = b/2$. At the boundaries $y = 0$ and $y = b$, the eigensolutions satisfies the conditions $Y_n = 0$ and

$$\frac{k_\theta}{D} \frac{\partial Y_n}{\partial y} \pm \frac{\partial^2 Y_n}{\partial y^2} = 0 \quad (4)$$

As shown in Faltinsen (1999), the eigensolution can be written in the form

$$Y_n(y) = \cos v + b_m \cosh v \quad (5)$$

where $v = \mu_n(y - b/2)/b$. In this case the eigenvalues μ_n satisfy the equation

$$\alpha [\cos(0.5 \mu_n) \tanh(0.5 \mu_n) + \sin(0.5 \mu_n)] \quad (6)$$

being $\alpha = 0.5k_\theta b/D$, and the constant $b_m = -\cos(0.5 \mu_n)/\cosh(0.5 \mu_n)$. In equation (4), k_θ is a spring stiffness of the restraint at the boundary.

Substitution of equation (2), together with equations (3) and (5), into the differential equation (1), leads to

$$\sum_m \sum_n W_{mn}(t) \left[\left(\frac{\lambda_m}{a} \right)^4 X_m(x) + \left(\frac{\lambda_m}{a} \right)^2 \left(\frac{\mu_n}{b} \right)^2 F_{mn}(x, y) + \left(\frac{\mu_n}{b} \right)^4 Y_n(y) \right] = \frac{p(x, y, t)}{D(x, y)} \quad (7)$$

It is worth noticing that although the thickness of the plate is uniform, in a region 75 mm wide all around the boundary there is the aluminum frame above, which is 10 mm thick. The presence of the frame is accounted for in equation (7) by using a local value of the flexural rigidity $D(x, y)$ based on the plate thickness $h_1 = 15$ mm in the inner region and $h_2 = 25$ mm in the frame region. When computing the eigenvalues from equation (6), an average flexural rigidity $D_{av} = (1 - \gamma)D_1 + \gamma D_2$ is employed, where $\gamma = 0.2$ is used. It has been found the parameter γ has a limited influence on the eigenvalues and does not affect the strains substantially.

In equation (7) the function F_{mn} comes from the second derivatives of the two eigenfunctions and it is given by

$$F_{mn} = [\cosh u + \cos u - a_m(\sinh u + \sin u)][-\cos v + b_n \cosh v] \quad (8)$$

The coefficients of the series W_{mn} are derived by enforcing equation (7) on the nodes of a $M \times N$ grid, M and N being much larger than m and n , and thus solving the overdetermined linear system by a least square approach. The parameter k_θ , the number of modes m and n to be used in the x and y directions as well as the number of grid points N and M are chosen to fit the data of one specific test and are used afterwards for the post-processing of all other test data.

3.2 Fluid-loading model

In order to provide the local pressure loading to the structural model at any time instant, a simplified model is adopted. Within the classical potential flow assumptions, the water entry problem of a two-dimensional, semi-infinite plate entering the water with a vertical velocity V and a constant horizontal velocity U , is self-similar if it is formulated in terms of new spatial variables $(\xi, \eta) = (x/Ut, y/Ut)$. The details of the problem formulation and its solution by a fully nonlinear boundary element method are discussed in Iafrati (2016). The self-similar solutions are computed for different V/U velocity ratios and pitch angles, and the corresponding pressure distributions and the force coefficients are derived along with some geometric parameters. It is shown that the pressure peak occurs at a point P which is just behind the spray root and propagates faster than the geometric intersection (G) between the plate and the still water level (Fig. 2).

By comparing the experimental measurements with the self-similar solution it is observed that, mainly due to the three-dimensional effects and the increased possibility for the fluid to escape from the side, the pressure peak propagation velocity is reduced and, consequently, pressure and force coefficients are also lower. In particular, the data in Iafrati (2016) show that the pressure peak propagation velocity starts from a value which is somewhat higher than the propagation velocity of the geometric intersection point, but approaches it soon after.

Fig 1: Self-similar solution of the ditching of a 2D plate infinite. The jet root, the thin spray and the free surface left behind the trailing edge T are highlighted. The pressure distribution (not in scale) is plotted above the plate.

Fig 2 a) Time histories of the pressure measured at the probes located at the middle of the plate. The passage of the pressure peak is clearly visible. Note that the origin of the time is set at the time when the pressure peak passes at probe P4. b) Time history of the total load acting on the plate. The data refer to the 10 degrees pitch angle, 40 m/s horizontal velocity and $V/U = 0.0375$

Based on the above considerations, the distribution of the forcing pressure to be used in equation (8) is derived by a mix between the self-similar solution and the experimental data. Although the measurements show a slight bending of the jet root line, it seems reasonable to assume the pressure to be uniform in the transverse direction. The distribution in the longitudinal direction is assigned by stretching the pressure profile of the self-similar solution so that, at each time, the position of the peak corresponds to the position of the pressure peak of the specific tests computed by linear interpolation of the times of the passage at the probes located at the middle of the plate (Fig. 3a). Finally, the pressure intensity is uniformly scaled so that the pressure integral over the plate equals the total force normal to the plate measured in the specific test (Fig. 3b).

4. DATA ANALYSIS

The model described in the previous section is validated and tuned in one test condition until a satisfactory agreement with the measurement is achieved. Specifically, test conditions are $U = 40$ m/s, $V/U = 0.0375$ and pitch angle 10 degrees, run 1132_02 (Iafrazi et al., 2015). It is found that $k_\theta = 100$ kN/rad provides a satisfactory representation of the elastic properties of the connections at the two lateral sides. For the derivation of the constants $W_{mn}(t)$ via the overdetermined linear system, a satisfactory convergence is achieved by using 20 grid points per mode in the corresponding direction.

The results in Fig. 4 and 5 show that in spite of the strong simplification and assumptions, the model is rather accurate. Some limitations appear nearby the boundary, particularly for S1, due to the difficulty in correctly representing the boundary conditions. In Fig. 4 the role played by the number of modes in the transverse direction is investigated. The results indicate that the number of modes does not affect the strains in the middle, but have some relevance at the side: the comparison in term of S6y shows that $n = 2$ is somewhat more representative than $n = 8$. This is probably because the loading is uniform in the y direction.

A similar analysis is done in Fig. 5 for the number of modes in the longitudinal direction. In this case the loading is characterized by a much sharper variation and indeed the results indicate that $m = 4$ modes are not enough, both at boundaries and in the middle of the plate, but there are no much changes for $m > 10$.

Once the coefficients $W_{mn}(t)$ are computed, they can be used to derive the out-of-plane displacement $w(x, y, t)$ and the strains everywhere along the plate. In Fig. 6 the contours of pressure distribution p , out-of-plane displacement w and strains s_x, s_y are drawn at $t \cong 0.06$ s which is about the time when strains at S5 attain their maxima and the pressure peak is at $x \cong 700$ mm, beneath S5.

Fig 3 Comparison of measured strains and the strains computed by the model. The role played by the number of modes n used in the y direction is highlighted ($m = 10$).

Despite the very localized loading, the deformation of the plate is much broader than the pressure peak, and the maximum displacement, which is about 3 mm, is behind the highest pressure region. This result indicates that indeed the out-of-plane displacement is smaller than the plate thickness, being beyond the 1/10 assumption, membrane effects might be not completely negligible. The strains behavior has expected based on the distribution of the displacement. The sharp variations occurring

nearby the boundary are due to the fact that strains are computed at the external layer of the plate using the local thickness, but this is not fully representative of the plate installation.

Fig 4 Comparison of measured strains with those computed by the model. The role played by the number of modes m used in the x direction is investigated here ($n = 2$).

Fig 5 Contours of pressure (kPa), out-of-plane displacement (m) and strains in x and y directions (m/m). Solution refers to $t \cong 0.06$ s.

5. CONCLUSIONS

A simplified model for the description of the structural response of a flat plate during high speed ditching tests has been developed and validated versus experimental measurements. The model is based on a combination of two models, one providing the hydrodynamic loading and the other representing the structural response. Aside from some limits related to the precise description of the boundary conditions, the model has been found rather efficient and accurate. The model is very helpful as it furnishes the strain field all along the plate, as well as the out-of-plane displacement which complement the experimental measurements. Being tuned and validated, the model can be used for the post-processing of the measurements done in the other test conditions, and then to investigate how the structural response changes when varying the impact conditions.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This project has received funding from the European Union's Seventh Framework Programme for Research and Technological Development under grant agreement No 266172 (FP7-SMAES) and from the Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under grant agreement No 724139 (H2020-SARAH)

REFERENCES

- CNR-INSEAN. (2012). *INSEAN report describing the design of the crane and the catapult system for guided ditching tests*.
- Faltinsen, O. M. (1999). Water Entry of a Wedge by Hydroelastic Orthotropic Plate Theory. *Journal of Ship Research*, 180-193.
- Faltinsen, O. M., Kvalsvold, J., & Aarsnes, J. V. (1997). Wave impact on a horizontal elastic plate. *J. Marine Science and Technology*, Vol.2, pp. 87-100.
- Iafrati, A. (2015). Fluid-structure interaction during the high speed water entry of a plate. *18th International Conference on Ships and Shipping Research*, (p. 197-206). Lecco (Italy): M. Altosole and A. Francescutto.
- Iafrati, A. (2016). Experimental investigation of the water entry of a rectangular plate at high horizontal velocity. *Journal of Fluid Mechanics*, Vol. 799, pp. 637-672.

- Iafrati, A., Fortunati, M., Olivieri, F., Santos, V. H., Grizzi, S., Sale, M., et al. (2014). *Data of the guided ditching tests for elastic specimens*. SMAES Deliverable D4.5.
- Iafrati, A., Grizzi, S., Siemann, M. H., & Benítez Montañés, L. (2015). High speed ditching of a flat plate: Experimental data and uncertainty assessment,. *Journal of Fluids and Structures*, Vol. 55, pp. 501-525.
- Kim, S., Novak, D., Weems, K., & Chen, H.-C. (2008). Slamming impact design loads on large high speed naval craft. *SuperFAST'2008, ABS Technical papers*, (p. pp. 207-218).
- Louarn, F., & Manganelli, P. (2010). A simplified slamming analysis model for curved composite panels. *21st International HISWA Symposium, Yacht design and yacht construction*.
- Seddon, C., & Moatamedi, M. (2006). Review of water entry with application to aerospace structures. *International J. of Impact Engineering*, Vol. 32, pp. 1045-1067.
- Stenius, I., Rosén, A., & Kuttenukeuler, J. (2011). Hydroelastic interaction in panel-water impacts of high speed craft. *Ocean Engineering*, Vol. 38, pp. 371-381.
- Szilard, R. (2004). *Theories and Applications of Plate Analysis: Classical, Numerical and Engineering Methods*. John Wiley & Sons, Inc.